

Supplementary materials

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A. Supplementary Table 1

EMA Subdimension	EMA Metric	EMA definition	Justification for excluding the definition
Accuracy	Plausibility checks	Number and percent of records with logical inconsistencies.	It is not possible to generalise the question for all the rare disease datasets
Accuracy	Plausibility checks	Number and percent of records where observed or derived values don't conform to expected temporal properties	Possible to adapt to Rare diseases field but not feasible for technical mapping
Accuracy	Plausibility checks	Number and percent of records where data values don't agree with common expectations (e.g., human with 4 arms)	It is not possible to generalise the question for all the rare disease datasets
Accuracy	Checks on dataset metadata	Number and percent of variables/datasets that are based on imputation or derivation	Metadata needed
Accuracy	Comparison to other data sources	Number and percent of records where corresponding variables yield identical results across independent or dependent databases	No other data sources available
Traceability	Checks on dataset metadata	Number and percent of datasets/variables for which traceability information is available in metadata.	Metadata needed
Completeness	Comparison to other data sources	Relative percentage of records for which a variable is missing with respect to a trusted source of knowledge	No other data sources available
Coverage	Comparison to other data sources	Percentage of a target population present in a database	No other data sources available
Format coherence (conformance)	Conformance checks	For relevant variables, % of records where that conform to formatting constraints	This definition can be mapped to the Genetic variables but there is no current data structural integrity
Relational coherence (conformance)	Independent data checks	Data values conform to relational constraints based on external standards	It is not possible to generalise the question for all the rare disease datasets

Uniqueness	Independent data checks	Number of records flagged as potential duplicates	Possible to adapt to Rare diseases field but not feasible for technical mapping
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Supplementary Table 1. Excluded metrics for the mapping between EMA and Rare Disease field and CARE-SM. The three first columns are the subdimension, metric and definition of the metric from EMA. And the last column is the justification of why this definition hasn't been added to the final mapping.

B. Supplementary Table 2

Rare Disease Definition	Rare Disease – CARE-SM property	SPARQL Query
% Patients with Disability Score above a certain threshold	Disability	<p>Query Treshold:</p> <pre>PREFIX sio: <http://semanticscience.org/resource/> PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/> SELECT (count(?val) as ?aboveValue) WHERE { ?attr a obo:NCIT_C21007. ?output sio:SIO_000628 ?attr. ?output sio:SIO_000300 ?val. FILTER(?val > %s) }</pre> <p>Query Total:</p> <pre>PREFIX sio: <http://semanticscience.org/resource/> PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/> SELECT (COUNT(?valTotal) AS ?numTotal) WHERE { ?attr a obo:NCIT_C21007. ?output sio:SIO_000628 ?attr. ?output sio:SIO_000300 ?valTotal. }</pre>
% Changes of Disability in a set of days	Disability	<pre>PREFIX ofn: <http://www.ontotext.com/sparql/functions/> PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/> PREFIX sio: <http://semanticscience.org/resource/> select (SUM(IF(?duration <= %s, 1, 0)) AS ?pairsUnderXDays) (COUNT(*) AS ?totalPairs) ((SUM(IF(?duration <= %s, 1, 0)) * 100 / COUNT(*)) AS ?percentageUnderXDays) where { Select distinct ?timeline ?enddate1 ?startdate2 ?duration WHERE { ?event1 a obo:NCIT_C25499. ?elem1 sio:SIO_000068 ?event1; sio:SIO_000681 ?end1; sio:SIO_000068 ?timeline. ?end1 sio:SIO_000300 ?enddate1. ?event2 a obo:NCIT_C25499. ?elem2 sio:SIO_000068 ?event2; sio:SIO_000680 ?start2; sio:SIO_000068 ?timeline. ?start2 sio:SIO_000300 ?startdate2. FILTER(?event1 != ?event2)</pre>

		<pre> FILTER (?enddate1 <= ?startdate2) BIND (ofn:daysBetween(?startdate2, ?enddate1) as ?duration) FILTER NOT EXISTS { ?event3 a obo:NCIT_C25499. ?elem3 sio:SIO_000068 ?event3; sio:SIO_000680 ?start3; sio:SIO_000681 ?end3; sio:SIO_000068 ?timeline. ?end3 sio:SIO_000300 ?enddate3. ?start3 sio:SIO_000300 ?startdate3. FILTER(?enddate1 < ?startdate3 && ?enddate3 < ?startdate2) } } } </pre>
% Duplicate Patient IDs	All variables	<pre> PREFIX sio: <http://semanticscience.org/resource/> PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/> select (COUNT(DISTINCT ?totalID) AS ?totalUniqueIDs) (COUNT(DISTINCT ?id) AS ?dupUniqueIDs) ((COUNT(DISTINCT ?id) * 100.0) / COUNT(DISTINCT ?totalID) AS ?duplicatePercentage) where { ?context a obo:NCIT_C62143. ?context sio:SIO_000068 ?time. ?time sio:SIO_000332 ?ind. ?ind sio:SIO_000671 ?totalID. OPTIONAL { SELECT ?context ?id WHERE { ?context a obo:NCIT_C62143. ?context sio:SIO_000068 ?time. ?time sio:SIO_000332 ?ind. ?ind sio:SIO_000671 ?id. } GROUP BY ?context ?id HAVING (COUNT(?id) > 1) } } </pre>
The number of decimal points used in data values, and their distribution	Corporal	<pre> PREFIX xsd: <http://www.w3.org/2001/XMLSchema#> SELECT DISTINCT ?decimals (COUNT(*) as ?count) WHERE { ?subject ?predicate ?value . FILTER(datatype(?value) = xsd:float) BIND(STR(?value) AS ?valStr) BIND(STRLEN(STRAFTER(?valStr, ".")) AS ?decimals) } group by ?decimals </pre>
CDE properties with missing values	All variables	<pre> Sex Total: PREFIX sio: <http://semanticscience.org/resource/> PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/> SELECT ?type (COUNT(?type) as ?countTotal) WHERE { ?out a ?type ; sio:SIO_000628 ?att . FILTER(?type = obo:NCIT_C160908) } GROUP BY ?onttype ?type Sex Threshold: PREFIX sio: <http://semanticscience.org/resource/> PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/> SELECT ?type (COUNT(?nullVar) as ?countTresh) WHERE { ?out a ?type ; sio:SIO_000628 ?att . </pre>

```
?att a ?onttype .
```

```
FILTER( ?type = obo:NCIT_C160908)
OPTIONAL{
  FILTER (
    (?onttype IN (
      obo:NCIT_C20197, # Male
      obo:NCIT_C16576, # Female
      obo:NCIT_C124294, # Unknown
      obo:NCIT_C17998 # Undifferentiated
    ))
  )
  BIND(?att AS ?nullVar)
}
}
GROUP BY ?type
```

birthdate Total:

```
PREFIX sio: <http://semanticscience.org/resource/>
PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/>
SELECT (COUNT(?att) AS ?countTotal)
WHERE {
  ?att a ?type .
  ?out sio:SIO_000628 ?att .
  FILTER(?type = obo:NCIT_C68615)
}
GROUP BY ?type
HAVING (COUNT(?att) > 0)
```

birthdate Threshold:

```
PREFIX sio: <http://semanticscience.org/resource/>
PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/>

select (COUNT(?val) AS ?countTresh)
where {
  ?att a ?type.
  ?out sio:SIO_000628 ?att .
  ?out sio:SIO_000300 ?val.

  FILTER(?type = obo:NCIT_C68615)
  FILTER( str(?val) != '' )
}
}
```

Id Total:

```
PREFIX sio: <http://semanticscience.org/resource/>
PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/>

SELECT (COUNT(?type) AS ?countTotal)
WHERE {
  ?variable a ?type ;
    sio:SIO_000020 ?role .
  ?ind a sio:SIO_000498 ;
    sio:SIO_000228 ?role .
  FILTER(?type = sio:SIO_000115)
}
GROUP BY ?type
HAVING (COUNT(?type) > 0)
```

Id Threshold:

```
PREFIX sio: <http://semanticscience.org/resource/>
PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/>

SELECT (COUNT(?value) AS ?countTresh)
WHERE {
  ?variable a ?type ;
    sio:SIO_000020 ?role .
  ?ind a sio:SIO_000498 ;
    sio:SIO_000228 ?role .
  ?variable sio:SIO_000300 ?value .
  FILTER(?type = sio:SIO_000115)
  Filter(str(?value) != '')
}
}
```

Disability Total:

```
PREFIX sio: <http://semanticscience.org/resource/>
PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/>
```

```
SELECT (COUNT(?type) AS ?countTotal)
WHERE {
    ?att a ?type .
    ?out sio:SIO_000628 ?att.
    FILTER(?type = obo:NCIT_C21007)
}
GROUP BY ?type
HAVING (COUNT(?type) > 0)
```

Disability Threshold:

```
PREFIX sio: <http://semanticscience.org/resource/>
PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/>
```

```
SELECT (COUNT(?value) AS ?countTresh)
WHERE {
    ?att a ?type .
    ?out sio:SIO_000628 ?att.
    ?out sio:SIO_000300 ?value.
    FILTER(?type = obo:NCIT_C21007)
    Filter(str(?value) != '')
}
}
```

Diagnosis Total:

```
PREFIX sio: <http://semanticscience.org/resource/>
PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/>
```

```
SELECT (COUNT(?type) as ?countTotal)
WHERE {
    ?out a ?type ;
    sio:SIO_000628 ?att .
    FILTER( ?type = obo:NCIT_C154625)
}
GROUP BY ?onttype ?type
```

Diagnosis Threshold:

```
PREFIX sio: <http://semanticscience.org/resource/>
PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/>
```

```
SELECT ?type (COUNT(?nullVar) as ?countTresh)
WHERE {
    ?out a ?type ;
    sio:SIO_000628 ?att .

    FILTER( ?type = obo:NCIT_C154625)
    OPTIONAL{
        ?att a ?onttype .
        FILTER (
            (?onttype IN (
                sio:SIO_000614
            ))
        )
        BIND(?att AS ?nullVar)
    }
}
GROUP BY ?type
```

Consent Total:

```
PREFIX sio: <http://semanticscience.org/resource/>
PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/>
```

```
SELECT (COUNT(?nullVar) as ?countTotal)
WHERE {
    ?out a ?type ;
    sio:SIO_000628 ?att .
    FILTER( ?type = obo:NCIT_C25460)
} GROUP BY ?onttype ?type
```

Consent Threshold:

```
PREFIX sio: <http://semanticscience.org/resource/>
PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/>
```

		<pre> SELECT ?type (COUNT(?nullVar) as ?countTresh) WHERE { ?out a ?type ; sio:SIO_000628 ?att . FILTER(?type = obo:NCIT_C25460) OPTIONAL{ ?att a ?onttype . } FILTER ((?onttype IN (obo:DUO_0000001, # Attribute obo:OBIB_0000488))) BIND(?att AS ?nullVar) } GROUP BY ?type Genetic Total: PREFIX sio: <http://semanticscience.org/resource/> PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/> SELECT (COUNT(?type) AS ?countTotal) WHERE { ?variable a ?type . ?variable sio:SIO_000229 ?out . FILTER(?type = obo:NCIT_C15709) } GROUP BY ?type HAVING (COUNT(?type) > 0) geneticQueryThreshold: PREFIX sio: <http://semanticscience.org/resource/> PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/> SELECT (COUNT(?value) AS ?countTresh) WHERE { ?variable a ?type . ?variable sio:SIO_000229 ?out . ?out sio:SIO_000671 ?value. FILTER(?type = obo:NCIT_C15709) Filter(str(?value) != 'T') } </pre>
<p>% Patients with multiple disability checks (No Disability, Multiple Checks and One check)</p>	<p>Disability</p>	<pre> Query Multiple Disabilities: PREFIX sio: <http://semanticscience.org/resource/> PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/> select (count(?idval) as ?totalID) where { SELECT ?idval (count(?idval) as ?countThreshold) WHERE { #Search Disability value ?attr a obo:NCIT_C21007. ?output sio:SIO_000628 ?attr; sio:SIO_000300 ?val. # Search individual related to the Disability Val ?id a sio:SIO_000115; sio:SIO_000300 ?idval; sio:SIO_000020 ?role. ?role sio:SIO_000356 ?proc. ?proc sio:SIO_000229 ?output. } }group by ?idval having(count(?val)>1) } Query One Disability: PREFIX sio: <http://semanticscience.org/resource/> PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/> select (count(?idval) as ?totalID) where { SELECT ?idval (count(?idval) as ?countThreshold) } </pre>

		<pre> WHERE { #Search Disability value ?attr a obo:NCIT_C21007. ?output sio:SIO_000628 ?attr; sio:SIO_000300 ?val. # Search individual related to the Disability Val ?id a sio:SIO_000115; sio:SIO_000300 ?idval; sio:SIO_000020 ?role. ?role sio:SIO_000356 ?proc. ?proc sio:SIO_000229 ?output. }group by ?idval having(count(?val)=1) } </pre> <p style="text-align: center;">Query 0 Disabilities:</p> <pre> PREFIX sio: <http://semanticscience.org/resource/> PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/> select (count(?idval) as ?totalID) where { SELECT distinct ?idval WHERE { ?id a sio:SIO_000115; sio:SIO_000300 ?idval; sio:SIO_000020 ?role. ?role sio:SIO_000356 ?proc. ?proc sio:SIO_000229 ?output. } group by ?idval } </pre>
<p>% HPO terms in the Phenotype property % NCIT terms in the Sex property</p>	<p>Phenotype Sex</p>	<p style="text-align: center;">Query HPO Terms:</p> <pre> PREFIX sio: <http://semanticscience.org/resource/> PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/> SELECT (count(?val) as ?countTotal) WHERE { ?spec a obo:NCIT_C16977. ?spec sio:SIO_000628 ?atr. ?atr a ?val. FILTER(regex(str(?val), "HP:")) } </pre> <p style="text-align: center;">Query Other Terms (not HPO):</p> <pre> PREFIX sio: <http://semanticscience.org/resource/> PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/> SELECT (count(?val) as ?countTotal) WHERE { ?spec a obo:NCIT_C16977. ?spec sio:SIO_000628 ?atr. ?atr a ?val. FILTER(! regex(str(?val), "HP")) FILTER(! regex(str(?val), "SIO_000614")) } </pre> <p style="text-align: center;">Query NCIT Terms:</p> <pre> PREFIX sio: <http://semanticscience.org/resource/> PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/> SELECT (count(?val) as ?countTotal) WHERE { ?spec a obo:NCIT_C160908. ?spec sio:SIO_000628 ?atr. ?atr a ?val. FILTER(regex(str(?val), "NCIT")) } </pre> <p style="text-align: center;">Query Other Terms (not NCIT):</p> <pre> PREFIX sio: <http://semanticscience.org/resource/> PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/> SELECT (count(?val) as ?countTotal) </pre>

		<pre> WHERE { ?spec a obo:NCIT_C160908. ?spec sio:SIO_000628 ?atr. ?atr a ?val. FILTER(! regex(str(?val), "NCIT")) FILTER(! regex(str(?val), "SIO_000614")) } </pre>
Check if the age is correct based on the date of birth and the date of the measurement.	Birth Date	<pre> PREFIX sio: <http://semanticscience.org/resource/> PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/> SELECT distinct ?indIDVal ?BirthDate ?ageValue ?startdate WHERE { #Find personId ?ID a sio:SIO_000115; sio:SIO_000300 ?indIDVal; sio:SIO_000020 ?role. ?role sio:SIO_000356 ?proc. ?proc sio:SIO_000229 ?out. #Retrieve Birth date ?attr a obo:NCIT_C68615. ?out sio:SIO_000628 ?attr. ?out sio:SIO_000300 ?BirthDate. # Context model ?indID a sio:SIO_000115; sio:SIO_000300 ?indIDVal. ?ind sio:SIO_000671 ?indID. ?timeline sio:SIO_000332 ?ind. ?elem sio:SIO_000068 ?timeline; sio:SIO_000687 ?age; sio:SIO_000680 ?start. ?age a obo:NCIT_C25150; sio:SIO_000300 ?ageValue. ?start sio:SIO_000300 ?startdate. } order by ?indIDVal </pre>
% ORDO terms in the Diagnosis property	Diagnosis;	<p style="text-align: center;">Query ORDO Terms:</p> <pre> PREFIX sio: <http://semanticscience.org/resource/> PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/> SELECT (count(?val) as ?countTotal) WHERE { ?spec a obo:NCIT_C154625. ?spec sio:SIO_000628 ?atr. ?atr a ?val. FILTER(regex(str(?val), "ORDO")) } </pre> <p style="text-align: center;">Query Other Terms (Not ORDO):</p> <pre> PREFIX sio: <http://semanticscience.org/resource/> PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/> SELECT (count(?val) as ?countTotal) WHERE { ?spec a obo:NCIT_C154625. ?spec sio:SIO_000628 ?atr. ?atr a ?val. FILTER(! regex(str(?val), "ORDO")) FILTER(! regex(str(?val), "SIO_000614")) } </pre>
Avg time between even Id (each time you go to a visit)	All models	<pre> PREFIX sio: <http://semanticscience.org/resource/> PREFIX ofn: <http://www.ontotext.com/sparql/functions/> # if daysBetween function available PREFIX obo: <http://purl.obolibrary.org/obo/> SELECT (AVG(?duration) AS ?averageGapInDays) WHERE { SELECT distinct ?timeline ?enddate1 ?startdate2 ?duration </pre>

		<pre> WHERE { ?event1 a obo:NCIT_C25499. ?elem1 sio:SIO_000068 ?event1; sio:SIO_000681 ?end1; sio:SIO_000068 ?timeline. ?end1 sio:SIO_000300 ?enddate1. ?event2 a obo:NCIT_C25499. ?elem2 sio:SIO_000068 ?event2; sio:SIO_000680 ?start2; sio:SIO_000068 ?timeline. ?start2 sio:SIO_000300 ?startdate2. FILTER(?event1 != ?event2) FILTER (?enddate1 <= ?startdate2) BIND (ofn:daysBetween(?startdate2, ?enddate1) as ?duration) # Only consecutive events: No intermediate event between date1 and date2 FILTER NOT EXISTS { ?event3 a obo:NCIT_C25499. ?elem3 sio:SIO_000068 ?event3; sio:SIO_000680 ?start3; sio:SIO_000681 ?end3; sio:SIO_000068 ?timeline. ?end3 sio:SIO_000300 ?enddate3. ?start3 sio:SIO_000300 ?startdate3. FILTER(?enddate1 < ?startdate3 && ?enddate3 < ?startdate2) } } </pre>
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Supplementary Table 2. SPARQL queries for the Rare disease and CARE-SM properties.